

GraspOS SCOPE+i Resource:

Guide on principles
for responsible
research
assessment for
evaluators and
evaluands

Full resource

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Introduction

Summary

Guide for evaluators and evaluands is a resource for supporting the evaluators and evaluands to be active participants of an assessment process. The aim of the guide is to help understand the basic framework of rules and principles of responsible research assessment (RRA) according to international and national legal regulations (e.g., laws and rights on gender equality and non-discrimination, European Charter for researchers), research integrity and ethics codes (e.g., All European Academies ALLEA), and key RRA and metrics recommendations (e.g., DORA, Leiden Manifesto, CoARA).

This guide is meant both for funders and employers as well as researchers (as reviewers and as subjects of evaluation). It defines the motivation and principles for RRA by introducing a relevant set of regulations and recommendations. What is RRA and why is there a need for assessment reform? How do different RRA initiatives try to tackle the issues in the current assessment system?

In addition, the roles and responsibilities of evaluators and evaluands are described, as stated in the RRA guidelines and principles. Although research funders and employers play a key role in shaping assessment culture, also researchers are active participants in the process, contributing to the development of assessment criteria and methods.

Guide as part of SCOPE+i Resources and in relation to SCOPE Framework

The [SCOPE+i Resources](#) aim to facilitate the transition towards Responsible Research Assessment (RRA) with particular focus on contributions to Open Science (OS). Being one out of 17 resources (guides, templates and checklists), this guide supports the awareness of both evaluators and evaluands of the key RRA principles and guidelines.

[SCOPE Framework](#) is a five-stage model for evaluating responsibly. It is a practical step-by-step process designed to help research managers, or anyone involved in conducting research evaluations, in planning new evaluations as well as checking existing evaluations. SCOPE is an acronym, where S stands for START with what you value, C for CONTEXT considerations, O for OPTIONS for evaluating, P for PROBE deeply, and E for EVALUATE your evaluation. This guide is most relevant for stages O and P.

Figure 1. SCOPE Framework by INORMS (2023) (modified by highlighting the most relevant stages for this resource).

More about SCOPE Framework in International Network of Research Management Societies (INORMS) - Research Evaluation Group (2023). The SCOPE Framework. The University of Melbourne. Report. <https://doi.org/10.26188/21919527.v1>

All SCOPE+i Resources are brought together in the [GraspOS Infrastructure](#) (i), a simple, user-friendly interface (UI) where you can explore project results and save documents to learn and share with others.

Collective agreements

All relevant actors in assessment processes (e.g., research funders, research performing organisations, HR professionals, evaluators and evaluands) should be aware of the principles of RRA and follow them as well as all the relevant requirements of collective agreements and legislation in the evaluation process.

This guide cites relevant EU laws related to, e.g., gender equality, and national laws and then concentrates more on policies and good practices. For the sake of keeping the guide as concise as possible, for collective agreements the focus is on the European and EU-level agreements.

The Charter of Fundamental Rights

[The Charter of Fundamental Rights](#) (European Union 2000) is the EU’s internal human rights agreement. It protects and promotes everyone’s fundamental rights within the EU. Chapter 3 of the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights is on equality. Concerning [non-discrimination](#) in the chapter on equality, “*any discrimination based on any ground such as sex, race, colour, ethnic or social origin, genetic features, language, religion or belief, political or any other opinion, membership of a national minority, property, birth, disability, age or sexual orientation shall be prohibited.*”

The European Union states about [Equality between women and men](#) the following: “*Equality between women and men must be ensured in all areas, including employment, work and pay. The principle of equality shall not prevent the maintenance or adoption of measures providing for specific advantages in favour of the under-represented sex. This right is enshrined in article 23 of the Charter of Fundamental Rights.*”

Please note that the national legislation of the relevant country can have specific additions.

The European Code of Conduct

The [European Commission](#) recognises [the European Code of Conduct](#) (ALLEA 2023) as the primary standard for upholding research integrity across all research projects funded by the EU.

Principles:

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1. **Reliability** in ensuring the quality of research, reflected in the design, methodology, analysis, and use of resources.
2. **Honesty** in developing, undertaking, reviewing, reporting, and communicating research in a transparent, fair, full, and unbiased way.
3. **Respect** for colleagues, research participants, research subjects, society, ecosystems, cultural heritage, and the environment.
4. **Accountability** for the research from idea to publication, for its management and organisation, for training, supervision, and mentoring, and for its wider societal impacts.

The European Code of Conduct increasingly serves as a model for national and institutional codes of conduct, funding guidelines, training initiatives, and discipline-specific standards. For example, the European Code of Conduct forms the foundation for detailed guidelines for [ROSiE General Guidelines on Responsible Open Science](#) (Bernabe et al. 2025), developed by the Horizon-funded ROSiE project. The ROSiE guidelines is the Open Science (OS) complement to the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity. It is an aspirational document that aims to provide guidance on how to conduct OS responsibly in everyday research practice, following established ethical and integrity principles and values (Bernabe et al. 2025).

Please see also [ROSiE Field-specific Guidelines on Responsible Open Science](#) (Rochambeau et al. 2025), which provide researchers with practical guidance, tailored to their discipline (Health and Life Sciences, Humanities, Natural Sciences, and Social Sciences), to implement responsible open science.

European Charter for researchers

The European Charter for Researchers is a set of principles underpinning the development of attractive research careers to support excellence in research and innovation across Europe. The focus of the European Charter for Researchers is the rights and responsibilities of researchers, employers, funders and policy makers.

The updated version of the European Charter for Researchers (European Union 2023) has been published as Annex II of [Council recommendation on a European framework to attract and retain research, innovation and entrepreneurial talents in Europe](#) (2023).

Based on The European Charter for Researchers (2023), employers and funders should “*support a system for the assessment and reward of researchers that considers the overall quality of their impact on society, science and innovation, the diversity of activities performed, Open Science practices, and the value of geographical, interdisciplinary and intersectoral mobility*”. In addition, to ensure coherence in the implementation of these principles, “*employers and funders should foster continuous training for the actors involved in the assessment and reward process.*”

What is responsible researcher assessment (RRA)?

Researchers are assessed in various contexts, for example when applying for positions or funding or when evaluated for a promotion, in tenure practices or personal performance. Research assessments entail important decisions about what matters (i.e., what should be valued in academic

careers and research outputs), about who decides what matters, and about how what matters can be measured (Aubert Bonn & Bouter 2023).

In many academic and research settings, evaluation systems have long relied heavily on quantitative metrics, such as journal impact factors, citation counts, h-index, often as proxies for quality. Over time, critiques have accumulated: these metrics can distort researcher behaviour (e.g., favouring quantity over quality, discouraging innovation or interdisciplinarity), misrepresent contributions, and exacerbate inequalities.

Thus, a reform movement has arisen to redefine what counts in assessing research and researchers, calling for more responsible, fair, and holistic assessment approaches. Curry et al. (2020) define RRA as “*umbrella term for approaches to assessment which incentivise, reflect and reward the plural characteristics of high-quality research, in support of diverse and inclusive research cultures.*”

Aubert Bonn & Bouter (2023) list five key issues that they believe to play an important part in the current discourse on research assessments:

1. **the exaggerated focus on research outputs**
 - a. Assessing researchers on the number of published papers does indeed lead to more publications, but it tends to do so at the detriment of research quality.
2. **the valuation of quantity over quality**
 - a. The longing for quantity also works in favour of predatory publishers and paper mills
3. **the inadequacy of currently used metrics**
 - a. For example, impact factors are a journal-level metric and are therefore not a valid measure for the impact of individual papers or of the authors of that paper.
4. **the narrow definitions of impact**
 - a. For example, the need to publish in high impact factor journals often translates in a need to publish in English-language international journals
5. **the obstacles current research assessments impose on diversity**
 - a. For example, gender inequalities are seen in both citation metrics and publication outputs. Diversity of skills, contribution, and career profiles is also an essential aspect that is largely ignored in current assessments and inclusion policies.

Please see Aubert Bonn & Bouter (2023) for more details.

Because of these and other issues, researchers and research communities joined forces to address these challenges and started demanding change in the way researchers are assessed (Aubert Bonn & Bouter 2023). This has led to RRA initiatives, of which the central ones are described in the “Key RRA principles and guidelines” section.

Key RRA principles and guidelines

The movement toward RRA is now well established internationally, with multiple influential initiatives offering overlapping but distinct perspectives (please see table 1).

The San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA 2012) sets out broad, ethical principles to move away from venue-based, journal impact factor driven assessment.

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The Leiden Manifesto (Hicks et al. 2015) provides ten guiding principles on the responsible use of metrics. **The Metric Tide** (Wilsdon et al. 2015) offers an evidence-based review of metrics in practice. **The Hong Kong Principles** (Moher et al. 2020) add emphasis on research integrity and rewarding trustworthy practices.

The Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment (ARRA, CoARA 2022) seeks to consolidate these efforts into common commitments and ensure implementation and accountability.

These initiatives do not stand alone; they often reference and build upon each other. For example, CoARA explicitly draws from DORA, Leiden Manifesto, and Metric Tide in forming its Agreement and Action Plans.

Common recurring themes include (see also table 1):

- Qualitative expert review over mechanical metrics.
- Diversity of outputs and contributions (not only journal articles, also datasets, software, community engagement, mentoring, peer review).
- Open science, transparency in research methodology, data, reporting.
- Context sensitivity: discipline, career stage, local relevance.
- Avoidance of perverse incentives and gaming, and attention to unintended consequences.

In addition to these core RRA initiatives, there are also initiatives closely related to RRA. The [Helsinki Initiative on Multilingualism in Scholarly Communication](#) (2019) provides recommendations promoting, e.g., language diversity, to be adopted by policy-makers, leaders, universities, research institutions, research funders, libraries, and researchers.

The signatories of [Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information](#) (2025) commit to taking a lead in transforming the way research information is used and produced. Openness of information about the conduct and communication of research must be the new norm. The declaration is important for RRA, because fair assessment of researchers and institutions requires full transparency.

Table 1. A visual summary table of the key points of the most relevant RRA principles and guidelines (DORA, The Leiden Manifesto, The Metric tide, The Hong Kong principles, Helsinki initiative, ARRA, Barcelona Declaration). Modified from Pölönen & Mustajoki (2022).

Recommendations		DORA (2012)	LEIDEN (2015)	METRIC TIDE (2015)	HONG KONG (2020)	HELSIN- KI (2019)	ARRA (2022)	BARCE- LONA (2025)
Method	Abandon journal metrics as surrogate measure of quality	✓					✓	
	Quantitative evaluation support qualitative assessment		✓	✓			✓	
	Qualitative judgment based on portfolios		✓					
	Misplaced concreteness and false precision		✓					
	Avoid using university rankings in researcher assessment						✓	
	Commit resources to reforming research assessment						✓	✓
	Raise awareness of research assessment reform						✓	
	Exchange practices and experiences to enable mutual learning						✓	
Support the sustainability of infrastructures for open research information							✓	
Criteria	Explicit criteria used in evaluation	✓						
	Systemics effects of assessment and indicators		✓	✓				
	Scrutiny and regular updating of indicators		✓	✓			✓	
Data	Open and transparent data and methods	✓		✓			✓	✓
	License allowing unrestricted reuse	✓						
	Allowing those evaluated to verify data and analysis		✓	✓				
	Best possible data in terms of accuracy and scope			✓				
Value diversity	All research outputs and broad range of impacts	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
	Missions of the institution, group researcher		✓					
	Excellence in locally relevant research		✓			✓		
	Variation by field in publication and citation practices		✓	✓				
	Plurality of research and career paths			✓			✓	
	Responsible practices, complete reporting, open science				✓		✓	
	Research activities and contributions				✓		✓	
Multilingualism and outputs in all languages					✓			

While these initiatives have made significant conceptual progress, challenges remain. These include, e.g., the following:

- Moving from principles to practice: institutional inertia, existing reward structures, hiring and promotion norms that still rely heavily on traditional metrics.
- Operationalizing new metrics or indicators that are reliable, fair, and broadly acceptable.
- Ensuring that reforms work well across diverse fields (especially SSH – social sciences & humanities) and in different regional, linguistic contexts.
- Monitoring and measuring the effects of reforms: what changes in researcher behaviour, publication practices, research culture.
- Resource and infrastructure requirements: to collect, verify, and manage new kinds of outputs, open data, peer review contributions etc.

Please see **GraspOS SCOPE+i Resource: Guide for overcoming common obstacles in implementing RRA** <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15526054> for more details.

Roles and responsibilities

Suggested summaries of recommendations for different roles (employer and funders, researchers as evaluators and researchers as the subjects of evaluation) based on e.g., sources presented in more detail in the relevant sections:

Employers and funders should, e.g.,

- Define the assessment protocol before evaluands are preparing data for assessment, and before evaluators start the assessment process
- Make sure that the assessment protocol includes, e.g., specification of indicators, criteria, diversity of the activity and outputs, defined value and purpose statement
- Check and deal with conflicts of interest beforehand
- Provide instructions on how to act and who to contact in cases of, e.g., suspected misconduct
- Communicate actively with reviewers and subjects of evaluation during the evaluation process

Researchers as evaluators should, e.g.,

- Read carefully all the relevant documents specifying assessment protocol
- Align understanding of rules and criteria between evaluators (if there is more than one evaluator) and with other actors participating in the preparation of the assessment protocol
- Claim to authorities or request additional explanation if something is not clear or transparent or does not comply with relevant RRA principles
- Report potential conflicts of interests and suspected misconducts at low threshold
- Pay attention to data confidentiality

Researchers as the subjects of evaluation should, e.g.,

- Read carefully all available instructions and prepare all the required documents in accordance
- Provide evidence whenever it is possible for any information provided in application
- Claim to authorities or request additional explanation if something is not clear or transparent or does not comply with relevant RRA principles
- Report potential conflicts of interests with potential reviewers

Research funders and research performing organisations

Employers and funders have a key role in creating a favourable environment for RRA especially by defining the assessment protocol and providing clear instructions for both reviewers and applicants.

Aubert Bonn & Bouter (2023) highlight the importance of defining key concepts as follows: *“training assessors to ensure that they have a clear understanding of the assessment process and providing unambiguous definition of the key concepts that are assessed (e.g., impact, excellence, quality, etc.) can help reduce biases”*.

DORA (2021) provides practical suggestions for research funders who are seeking to implement or improve responsible assessment of funding applications:

- Align decision-making to **strategic objectives and specific criteria** of the funding institution or instrument.
- Be clear about the **context and limitations of any quantitative metrics** used and **balance them with qualitative** parts of the funding proposal.
- Look broadly to include **research activities beyond publications** and grants to capture the full range of a researcher’s contributions.

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- Be aware of **biases that arise from scientific and cultural stereotypes**.
- Promote **personal and group accountability** for responsible research assessment during evaluation.

Recommendations for employers and funders stated in the European Charter for Researchers (European Union 2023)

- Employers and funders should support, provide the necessary tools and infrastructure, and **reward a true Open Science culture** across the Union, including mainstreaming open access to scholarly publications, research data and other research outputs.
- Employers and funders should **encourage and support non-linear and multi-career paths**.
- **assessment should be based primarily on qualitative judgement**, for which peer review and review by other pertinent experts is central, supported by the responsible use of quantitative indicators.
- Employers and funders are recommended to establish **recruitment and selection procedures which are open, transparent and merit-based**, without penalisation for career breaks or non-linear, multi-career and hybrid paths.
- **Selection committees should also have adequate gender balance** and, where appropriate and feasible, include members from different sectors – public and private – and disciplines, and from other countries.
- Employers and funders should recognise that **researchers may have highly diverse careers** both in research and in other functions.
- Employers and funders should ensure that all researchers at any stage of their career, regardless of their contractual situation, are given the **opportunity for professional development** and for improving their employability through access to measures for the continuing development of skills and competencies.
- Employers and funders should ensure that **teaching duties are adequately remunerated** and considered in the evaluation/appraisal systems from an early stage of researchers' careers.

Recommendations by Science Europe (2020)

- Research organisations should **streamline assessment processes** to reduce the burden on reviewers and applicants. **Standardisation and interoperability** of such processes within and between organisations should be considered.
- Research assessment processes must be **clear and transparent** at all stages, for all involved.
 - Organisations should publish **accessible and user-friendly guides** to all the processes that they follow when performing assessments.
 - These guides should be made public and include **descriptions of the criteria** (and scoresheets, where applicable) used to make assessments.
 - Organisations should **monitor and evaluate the efficacy of the guidance** they provide, and consider different and innovative means of displaying and disseminating such information (video or interactive webpages, for instance) to ensure that all relevant parties can be appropriately informed.
- Organisations should transparently **define the meaning of any general terms** they use to describe levels of research attainment/achievement and should be cautious if using such

terms ('excellence', for example) in isolation as a specific criterion within assessment processes.

- Definitions will 1) help reviewers to understand the targets of specific assessment schemes, and 2) aid applicants in understanding the relevance of different schemes to them.
- Organisations should be clear in highlighting where different schemes within their organisation use different criteria to determine quality (i.e. discipline-specific or career-stage-specific criteria).
- Organisations should **provide precise definitions** of what constitutes a conflict of interest, and ensure that everyone involved in assessment processes is suitably informed to be able to identify them.
 - Applicants may be given the opportunity to **suggest and justify the exclusion of certain experts** from the assessment of their applications, but responsibility for conflict-of-interest identification should be held at organisation level.
- Research assessments should **focus on the substance and content** of applications. Processes should **aid reviewers in conducting qualitative assessments** that consider a broad spectrum of research outputs and activities.
- Research organisations should consider implementing **novel assessment techniques**. Methodologies and outcomes of these should be shared to promote mutual learning.
- Research organisations should publicly demonstrate and continually evaluate how they **address bias, discrimination, and unfair treatment** in assessment processes. Updated **guidelines and training** should be available to all involved.
- **Broader criteria for the selection of appropriate reviewers** should be considered, emphasising the importance of international reviewers. **Review activity should be appropriately recognised**.
- Organisations should consider the inclusion of a 'right-to-reply' mechanism in assessment processes to improve the quality of assessments.
- Organisations should **publish the general results for all assessment processes**. Further, **all applicants should be given an assessment report** with the result of their application, regardless of whether they were successful or not.
 - For open calls, year-on-year comparative selection rates by research field or discipline and gender may be a useful metric for comparing assessment schemes, for example.
 - Assessment reports can be helpful for both successful and unsuccessful candidates in future applications and can also help to justify the time and effort put into application processes. Such reports should be informative, but must not unnecessarily overburden research organisations. Reports could be scaled to size of the scheme applied for, for instance.
- Research organisations should continually **monitor and regularly evaluate** the robustness of their assessment processes, and **share best practices** to foster mutual learning.

Please see also **Funding by Algorithm - A handbook for responsible uses of AI and machine learning by research funders** (RoRI 2025) for case studies of diverse real-world applications of AI/ML by research funders and takeaways, recommendations and future directions for funders seeking to explore or apply AI/ML in their work.

Researchers

Researchers, especially when acting as evaluators or reviewers, have a direct relevance to assessment processes. Researchers are not just subjects of evaluation but also active participants in the process, contributing to the development of assessment criteria and methods (see, e.g. Good Practice in Researcher Evaluation: Recommendation for the Responsible Evaluation of a Researcher in Finland, Working group for responsible evaluation of a researcher 2020). Thus, researchers should advocate for responsible research assessment practices that consider the broader impact of their work, beyond traditional metrics like journal impact factors (Working group for responsible evaluation of a researcher 2020).

People are always subject to unconscious bias. As Aubert Bonn & Bouter (2023) state, “*when reflective and qualitative peer-review takes precedence, a great deal of subjectivity is introduced in the assessment process. Subjectivity is not a bad thing but it leaves substantial room for personal biases and involuntary discrimination in research assessments*”. Recognizing unconscious biases is the first step to reduce them.

Diversity is important in trying to reduce the influence of biases. Many guidelines recommend that research and funding organisations should strive to ensure that reviewer pools and hiring committees contain diverse profiles (Science Europe 2020). Diversity in this context does not mean only gender and ethnicity, but also for example the profiles of assessors and their seniority (Aubert Bonn & Bouter 2023).

Also raising awareness, training, and providing guidance for reviewers are important ways to reduce unconscious biases. When acting as a reviewer or a member of an assessment panel, researchers can ask for relevant guidelines from the relevant institution and question for e.g., the lack of diversity in the assessment team.

DORA recommendations for researchers (DORA 2012):

- When involved in committees making decisions about funding, hiring, tenure, or promotion, **make assessments based on scientific content rather than publication metrics**.
- **Challenge research assessment practices that rely inappropriately on Journal Impact Factors** and promote and teach best practice that focuses on the value and influence of specific research outputs.
- If you are not sure whether you have a **conflict of interest** or not, ask the funding institution for guidance.

Principles for reviewing and assessment in [The European Code of Conduct](#) (ALLEA 2023)

- Researchers take seriously their commitment and responsibility to the research community through refereeing, reviewing, and assessment, and **this work is recognised and rewarded** by researchers, research institutions, and organisations.
- Researchers, research institutions, and organisations review and assess submissions for publication, funding, appointment, promotion, or reward in a **transparent and justifiable manner**, and disclose the use of AI and automated tools.

- Reviewers and editors **declare any actual or perceived conflicts of interest** and, when necessary, withdraw from involvement in discussion and decisions on publication, funding, appointment, promotion, or reward.
- Reviewers **maintain confidentiality** unless there is prior approval for disclosure.
- Reviewers and editors **respect the rights of authors and applicants**, and seek permission to make use of the ideas, data, or interpretations presented.
- Researchers, research institutions, and organisations **adopt assessment practices that are based on principles of quality**, knowledge advancement, and impact that go beyond quantitative indicators and take into account diversity, inclusiveness, openness, and collaboration where relevant.

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